

The Early Christian basilicas of Amathous

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Entry tags: Basilica, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Early Christianity, Cyprus, Monastery, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Christian Traditions, Religious Place, Shrine, Religious Complex

Amathous, on the south coast of Cyprus, was an ancient city and one of the ancient royal cities of the island, which became home to the homonymous bishopric in the 4th century CE. Among the city's impressive remains are the five Early Christian basilicas. The first, situated at the Acropolis of the city was uncovered by the French Archaeological mission in 1975. This is the latest of the Amathous basilicas built during the late 6th or the early 7th century CE on the foundations of the temple of Aphrodite, destroyed by an earthquake in the 6th century CE. The three-aisled basilica (25m by 24m) with the opus sectile flooring, the wall and apse mosaics and the champlévé revetments possessed a narthex, an exonarthex and several annexes. A stairway was connecting the west side of the building to the gallery above the side aisled and the narthex. The complex included additional rooms, a large cistern, and a rainwater catchment system. The basilica was abandoned at the end of the 7th century CE, prior to its destruction, for unknown reasons. The other four basilicas were excavated by the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus. The three aisled basilica (nave and aisles: 11.5m by 17m), partially built into the bedrock at the base of the Acropolis, west of the Agora, was excavated in 1961. It was dated to the end of the 4th century or the beginning of the 5th century CE. The basilica possessed a narthex and an exonarthex and an apsidal chapel, adjacent to the south side. The walls featured mosaic and marble decoration. The south nave was adorned with reliefs depicting a hunting scene, dated to the mid-5th to the early 6th century CE. The floor of the sanctuary was paved with opus sectile. The great three-aisled basilica at the east of the Agora was excavated at the beginning of the 1990's. It was dated to the second half of the 5th century CE and is believed that it was destroyed by the Arabs between 653-654 CE. It seems that renovation has taken place soon after its destruction, while the church continued being used for some decades. This is one of the largest basilicas of Cyprus (c. 1750m²), built on the foundations of an earlier phase. The basilica possessed a baptistery, a narthex and atrium at the west side. The three aisles were paved with opus sectile. The oldest of the Amathous basilicas is the one dedicated to saint Tychon († c.425 CE), second bishop of Amathous. This is the only shrine of the island dedicated to the saint. It was excavated between 1991 and 1995. Located extra muros, north of the east gate of Amathous and adjoining a necropolis, the building which still stands today dates to the Frankish period (late 14th-early 15th century CE). The two prior phases are going back to the Early Christian period: Phase I from the late 4th or early 5th century CE; Phase II from the second half of the 5th century CE. The initial three-aisled building is most likely similar in size to the basilica at the base of the Acropolis, although it is difficult to clearly distinguish all the elements of the initial church. In Phase II, which may date around the death of saint Tychon in 450 CE, was erected the largest three-aisled basilica that included a martyrium. The basilica was destroyed during the Arab raids of 653-654 CE. It was repaired and remained in use until the 13th century CE. It was abandoned for a small period, before the erection of the Frankish church. The small five-aisled basilica of saint Barbara, in the east of Amathous, was uncovered between 1973-1974. Although its dedication is unknown, it was named after the nearby cave dedicated to saint Barbara. The sanctuary had mosaic flooring. It may have been a destination for the infirm as evidenced by the archaeological findings representing human parts. The presence of adjoining spaces, cisterns and an olive pressing suggest that the church belonged to a monastery. The basilica was likely constructed between the 5th and the 6th century CE.

Date Range: 300 CE - 800 CE
Region: Amathous, Cyprus
Region tags: Europe
Amathous, Cyprus

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation
- Body of water (as distinct from source)
- Cave
- Other [specify]: Coastline

- ↳ Type of elevation
 - Hill

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: Five Early Christian basilicas

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - Yes

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Other [specify]: Earthquakes, raids

 - ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - For religious reasons
 - As the result of war
 - As the result of pillage

 - ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saint Tychon, saint Barbara and also to other unknown saints

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Chotzakoglou, Ch, "Αμαθούς, βασιλικές (Κύπρος)" in Μεγάλη Ορθόδοξη Χριστιανική Εγκυκλοπαίδεια, vol. 2, Athens, 2010, 229-230.

– Source 2: Procopiou, E., "Eglise d' Ayios Tychonas" in P.Aupert (ed.), Guide d' Amathonte, Paris, 1996,

– Source 3: Procopiou, E., "Η εκκλησιαστική αρχιτεκτονική στη Βυζαντινή Επαρχία Αμαθούντας 4ος-12ος, Αρχαιολογική Έρευνα 1991-2012", Επετηρίδα Κέντρου Μελετών Ιεράς Μονής Κύκκου 11, 2016, 9-34

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Water feature

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.efa.gr/en/recherche/sites-de-fouilles/chypre/amathonte>

– Source 1 Description: French archaeological mission in Cyprus. Excavation history at Amathous

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.mcw.gov.cy/mcw/DA/DA.nsf/All/D20ED526826AB796C225719B00374A92?OpenDocument>

– Source 2 Description: Brief description of the site provided by the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1961-today

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Amathous or Amathounta

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

–Other [specify]: Christians

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

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- Source 1: Chotzakoglou, Ch, "Αμαθούς, βασιλικές (Κύπρος)" in Μεγάλη Ορθόδοξη Χριστιανική Εγκυκλοπαίδεια, vol. 2, Athens, 2010, 229-230.
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Topographical Context

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– Clearing
– Trackway or road-surface
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↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

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– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Five Early Christian basilicas

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↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

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Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

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↳ Worship:

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↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

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↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– As the result of war

– As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saint Tychon, saint Barbara and also to other unknown saints

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↳ Is it a cenotaph:

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↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

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A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

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↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: Christians

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

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Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

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Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– I don't know

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract
– Yes

↳ Floral motifs
– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
– No

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: nothing else to mention

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
– No

↳ Are there statues present:
– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:
– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: reliefs exclusively decorative

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: mosaics with geometric and floral elements

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: marble

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– I don't know

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

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Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: marble

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– I don't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– I don't know

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: nothing else to mention

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: reliefs exclusively decorative

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:
– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
– Other [specify]: mosaics with geometric and floral elements

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– No

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:
– No

Are pilgrimages present:
– No

Is divination present:
– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Once a year on Saint Tychon's and saint Barbara's feast day

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: through services and liturgies

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

–specify: once a year, on Saint Tychon's and Saint Barbara's feast day

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–All members

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

–number: Unknown

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: It is believed that the basilica of saint Tychon was the palce of his burial and of the burial of the bishops of Amathous.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Notes: It is believed that the basilica of saint Tychon was the palce of his burial and of the burial of the bishops of Amathous.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

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↳ Through divination practices:

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Are previously human spirits present:

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Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Once a year on Saint Tychon's and saint Barbara's feast day

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: once a year, on Saint Tychon's and Saint Barbara's feast day

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Unknown

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– I don't know

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– I don't know

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

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General References

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